

PREDICTION OF NON-LINEAR BEHAVIOUR OF DISCONTINUOUS LONG GLASS FIBRES POLYPROPYLENE COMPOSITES

E. Jao Jules¹, S. V. Lomov¹, I. Verpoest¹, P. Naughton², A. W. Beekman³, R. Van Daele³

¹*Department of Metallurgy and Materials Engineering (MTM), Katholieke Universiteit Leuven, Kasteelpark Arenberg, 44 B-3001 Heverlee, Belgium*

²*Dow Automotive, Schwalbach, Germany*

³*Dow Benelux N.V., Terneuzen, The Netherlands*

SUMMARY: In the present work, the non-linear behaviour of discontinuous long fibre composites is investigated using a micromechanical analysis based on the Eshelby inclusion model. From this a model was developed, based on the Mori and Tanaka method, to predict the stress-strain curves of long glass fibre polypropylene (LGFPP) composites including matrix non-linearity and damage. The non-linear behaviour of the matrix is modelled by using the experimental stress-strain curve of the polypropylene and the tangent modulus method. The damage created during deformation is mainly fibre breakage and interfacial debonding, leading to an additional stiffness reduction of the composite. To understand the influence of the microstructure on the final mechanical properties of the composite, the effects of fibre length and fibre orientation distributions are studied. The mechanical properties of LGFPP composites vary with its local microstructure, hence they are process dependent. The model predictions are good compared to the experimental results.

KEYWORDS: discontinuous fibres, stress, strain, non-linear, debonding, Mori and Tanaka.

INTRODUCTION

Mean-field approaches are extensively used to evaluate the overall elastic properties of composite materials [1, 2, 3]. They are all based on the assumption that the stress and strain fields in the matrix and in the reinforcement are represented by their volume-averaged values, but they differ by the way they account for the interaction between the phases. Using Eshelby inclusion method and Mori and Tanaka mean field theory, we developed a model allowing the computation of the effective linear elastic properties of discontinuous long fibre composites taking into account the length as well as the orientation distributions of the fibres [4].

Most of polymer matrices reinforced with discontinuous long fibres have a non-linear behaviour under mechanical loading. Therefore the understanding of the overall non-linear mechanical behaviour of LGFPP composite materials is important for the prediction of strength and damage development. For that reason, a linear elastic model, developed previously, had to be extended to take into account the non-linearity of the matrix. However, the difficulty in solving non-linear problems makes it impossible to obtain the exact solutions by analytical models for such composite with non-regular microstructures, which moreover depend on processing conditions. Several models based on approximation or linearization instead of finding the exact solutions were developed in the past, among which the secant and

the tangent modulus methods. Tandon and Weng [5] developed the well known secant modulus method to predict plastic behaviour of composites by using the linear effective properties of a comparison composite to evaluate its non-linear properties. The idea in the secant method is to use a stiffness or compliance tensor, dependent on the accumulated plastic strain, to get the relationship between the stress and strain in each phase and in the composite. In the tangent method, each phase follows the incremental theory of plasticity and the composite behaviour is obtained incrementally by integrating along the loading path the composite stiffness tensor resulting from the tangent stiffness tensors of each phase.

This paper focuses on the theoretical prediction of the tensile behaviour of LGFPP composite materials. Since the matrix and the interface mainly dominate the mechanical behaviour of such composites we will consider the non-linearities, coming from the matrix behaviour and from the damage development in the fibres and on the interface between the fibres and the matrix. The non-linearity of the matrix is first implemented in the Mori and Tanaka model by using the tangent method, instead of using the Young's modulus of the polymer, in an incremental formulation. The effect of fibre length on the non-linear behaviour is investigated for different constant fibre length values and also for a representative fibre length distribution. Finally, the fibre/matrix debonding is implemented using a suitable failure criterion for the interface and stiffness degradation of the material is predicted.

MATERIALS

The material of the study is an injection moulded long glass fibres reinforced polypropylene, produced by injection moulding. It is known that during the injection moulding process fibre breakage occurs and that the fibre orientation strongly depends on the local flow conditions; hence it is important that the model takes into account the fibre length distribution as well as the fibre orientation distribution.

Matrix and fibres data used in the micro-mechanical calculations are listed in *Table 1*. The matrix and the fibres are assumed to be isotropic. The polypropylene has a non-linear behaviour with an initial Young's modulus given in *Table 1*. The non-linear stress-strain curve of the polypropylene used in the calculations is shown in the next section.

Table 1: Properties of the polypropylene and the glass fibres

	Matrix	Fibres
R_o (g/cm ³)	0.9	2.54
$E = E_t$ (MPa)	1450	70 000
$P_o = P_{ot}$	0.33	0.23
$G = G_t$ (MPa)	588	29 268
d (mm)		0.017
Fibre content per weight (%)		30

Where R_o is the density of the material, P_o and P_{ot} are the longitudinal and transverse Poisson ratio respectively, G and G_t are the longitudinal and transverse shear moduli respectively, d is the diameter of the fibres (the same for all the fibres).

The fibre length distribution used in the modelling is given in *Fig. 1*. *Fig. 2* shows how the orientations of the fibres are defined. Using this definition of orientation, calculations were done for a composite with a tensile bar orientation, with all the fibres oriented in the plane ($\theta = 90^\circ$ for all the fibres) and φ distribution as shown in *Fig. 3*.

Fig. 1: Fibre length distribution (in mm)

Fig. 2: Definition of the orientations of a fibre, with φ the in plane orientation and θ the out plane orientation. Axis 1 represents the injection direction, Axis 3 is the direction through the thickness.

Fig. 3: In plane fibre orientation (φ) distribution

MATRIX NON-LINEARITY

The contribution of the matrix properties to the overall composite behaviour is really important since the yielding of the matrix will lead to a drop of the effective stiffness of the composite. Consequently it is important to take into account the matrix non-linear behaviour. To investigate the influence of the yielding of the matrix on the tensile behaviour of LGFPP composites, the non-linear stress-strain behaviour of the polypropylene (Fig. 4) associated with the tangent method has been implemented first in an incremental Mori and Tanaka model. The tangent method was chosen because it takes into account the load path, which is useful for further damage implementation in the model in order to account for the stiffness reduction of the composite. With this non-linear model, the undamaged, non-linear stiffness of the composite was predicted as explained with the basic equations below.

Consider a certain stage of deformation of composite (defined by a stress σ applied to the composite). The effective stiffness of the composite material, is defined by

$$\sigma = C^{eff} \varepsilon \quad (1)$$

and using Mori and Tanaka approach [1]

$$C^{eff} = C^m + v^f [C^f - C^m] A_{dilute} [v^m I + v^f A_{dilute}]^{-1} \quad (2)$$

with v^f the volume fraction of fibres, v^m the volume fraction of matrix, C^f the stiffness of the fibre, C^m the stiffness of the matrix, A_{dilute} the concentration tensor approximated by using the dilute approximation and the Eshelby method as

$$A_{dilute} = [I + S(C^m)^{-1} [C^f - C^m]]^{-1} \quad (3)$$

where S is the Eshelby tensor. The first step in the incremental calculation is to calculate the average strain of the matrix as

$$\varepsilon^m = [v^m C^m + v^f \langle C^f A_{dilute} \rangle]^{-1} \sigma \quad (4)$$

with σ the stress applied to the composite material

The tangent modulus of the matrix is calculated from the effective strain using the experimental tensile curve (*Fig. 4*). The overall tangent compliance of the composite is then obtained from the inverse of Eqn. (2) and composite strain for the given stress σ can be found by equation (1). The applied stress is then increased and the calculation is repeated.

Fig. 4: Experimental tensile curve of polypropylene matrix

DAMAGE MODELLING

There are several types of damage (matrix failure, fibre pull-out, fibre breakage, interfacial degradation...) which can occur in composite materials leading to a degradation of its overall mechanical properties. Fibre breakage has to be considered since it reduces the efficiency of the fibre-matrix load transfer. Moreover, in case of discontinuous long fibre composites, the interface between the matrix and the fibre is a critical zone for damage accumulation. Consequently, to model correctly the mechanical behaviour of the composite material, the fibre-matrix debonding as well as the fibre breakage must be taken into account.

Fibre breakage

The average stress inside the fibre σ^{in} is evaluated according to the following equation:

$$\sigma^{in} = C^m (\epsilon^m + (S - I) \epsilon^*) \quad (5)$$

with ϵ_{ij}^* the transformation strain, obtained as follow:

$$\epsilon^* = -\left[(C^f - C^m)S + C^m \right]^{-1} (C^f - C^m) \epsilon^m \quad (6)$$

To check if fibre breakage occurred, the stress value in the fibre is compared to the fibre strength. When the stress inside the fibre exceeds the fibre strength, the fibre is then split up in two short fibres with the same properties but half-length value of the original one.

Fibre-matrix debonding

The interfacial strength, which is related to the properties of the matrix, is important for the properties and the strength of the composite. For that reason, in this paper, the fibre/matrix debonding is investigated. The debonding mechanism is quite well understood on the microscopic level [6] and our model is based on a simple approach using well known equations in order to better understand the debonding mechanism in LGFPP composite. The first step in the approach consists of calculating the interfacial stress tensor. Once the stress tensor is evaluated at the interface, a suitable debonding criterion is chosen to describe the debonding phenomenon. Finally a treatment for the debonded fibre leading to the stiffness reduction of the composite is proposed.

Interfacial stress tensor

The interfacial stress tensor is calculated using the normal stress-continuity condition at the interface. With this method it is not necessary to know the exact stress field in the matrix surrounding the fibre. The stress tensor just outside the fibre is then obtained by [7] [8]:

$$\sigma_{ij}^{out} = \sigma_{ij}^{in} + C_{ijkl}^m \epsilon_{ij}^{int} \quad (7)$$

where σ_{ij}^{in} is defined by Eqn.5, and ϵ_{ij}^{int} is the displacement gradient tensor across the interface given by:

$$\epsilon_{ij}^{int} = -C_{pqmn}^m \epsilon_{mn}^* M_{ip} n_q n_j + \epsilon_{ij}^* \quad (8)$$

with the tensor M_{ip} for an isotropic matrix defined by:

$$M_{ip} = \frac{1}{G_m} \left[\delta_{ip} - \frac{n_i n_p}{2(1-\nu_m)} \right] \quad (9)$$

in which G_m and ν_m are respectively the shear modulus and the Poisson ratio of the matrix, δ_{ip} is the Kronecker delta and n_i are the components of the outward unit vector normal to the fibre surface (given later in Eqn. 14).

Interfacial debonding criterion

Coulomb's criterion is chosen since it takes into account the normal debonding as well as the shear slip:

$$\sigma_N + k\tau \leq \sigma^* \quad (10)$$

with σ_N (Eqn. 11) and τ (Eqn.12) respectively the normal and tangential components of the stress just outside the fibre (Eqn. 7), k is the shear contribution coefficient, σ^* the fibre-matrix interfacial strength.

$$\sigma_N = \sigma_i^{out} n_i = \sigma_{ij}^{out} n_j n_i \quad (11)$$

$$\tau = \sqrt{\|\sigma_i^{out}\|^2 - \sigma_N^2} \quad (12)$$

The Coulomb's criterion is applied at several locations along the fibre as shown in Fig. 5.

Fig. 5: Positions along the inclusion where fibre-matrix debonding is checked ($z = 0, z1=L/4, z2=3L/8, z3=7L/16, z4=15L/32, z5=31L/64$)

For each position along the fibre, the Coulomb criterion is applied again at numerous points on the circular cross-section of the fibre. From a computational point of view, the number of surface sections checked is set to 12. The surface sections are equally spaced and for practical purposes, it has been found that three sections per quadrant are sufficiently accurate for φ_1 and φ_2 defined as [9]:

$$\varphi_1 = 30^\circ \text{ and } \varphi_2 = 60^\circ \quad (13)$$

with φ_1 and φ_2 the local in-plane angles for the first quadrant of the circular cross-section (Fig. 6).

Each surface section is defined by the outward normal to the surface of the ellipsoid (Fig. 6), and components of the outward normal are calculated in the local fibre co-ordinate system according to:

$$\begin{bmatrix} n_1 \\ n_2 \\ n_3 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} x/\text{denom1} \\ y/\text{denom1} \\ z/\text{denom2} \end{bmatrix} \quad (14)$$

with $\text{denom1} = d^2 \sqrt{\frac{x^2 + y^2}{d^4} + \frac{z^2}{l^4}}$ and $\text{denom2} = l^2 \sqrt{\frac{x^2 + y^2}{d^4} + \frac{z^2}{l^4}}$, d : the diameter of the fibre, l : the length of the fibre and x, y, z the point coordinates defined as follow:

$$\begin{cases} x = r \cos(\varphi) \\ y = r \sin(\varphi) \\ z \end{cases}$$

with r the radius of the cross section of the fibre of coordinate z defined by: $r = \frac{d}{2} \sqrt{1 - \frac{z^2}{(l/2)^2}}$

Fig. 6: Determination of the outward normal $\bar{n}(\varphi, \theta)$ on a circular fibre cross-section for a certain position along the fibre

If the Coulomb criterion is satisfied in one location along the fibre or in one surface section on the cross-section of the fibre, then the fibre is considered partially debonded. The treatment of debonded fibres have been subject of discussion, and generally in the models found in the literature, effective properties of damaged interfaces have been modelled either by using an additional interface with degraded properties, or by replacing the debonded isotropic fibre by an equivalent perfectly bonded orthotropic fibre having a different contribution into the overall composite stiffness [10] [11]. Calculations of properties of debonded interfaces often based on assumed conditions were performed ranging from partial [12] to complete loss of load-transfer (in the direction of debonding).

In our approach, once debonded the isotropic fibre is replaced by isotropic matrix decreasing hence the total volume fraction of fibres in the unit cell (which is adjusted in the further calculations), and consequently reducing the overall stiffness of the composite. The analysis is then continued in a similar way for the remaining non-debonded fibres.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Matrix non-linearity

To check the non-linear model before damage is included in it, calculations were done for different LGFPP composites with small (0.5 mm), medium (3 mm), high (30 mm) constant fibre length values, and for a representative fibre length distribution. The fibre length and orientations distributions, presented in *Fig. 1* and *Fig. 3*, were used in the calculations. The predicted stress-strain curves are plotted in *Fig. 7*, in the following order from the bottom: 0.5 mm, distribution, 3 mm, 30 mm, which shows the effect of the fibre length on the non-linear behaviour of the LGFPP composite. The predictions are in agreement with the known result stating that the shorter the fibres the more non-linear is the behaviour of the composite. *Fig 8* shows the prediction of the stress-strain curve for a simple tensile bar before the introduction of damage. The initial part of the curve closely follows the experimental data. The prediction remains quite stiff as the strain increases indicating the absence of the damage compared to tests.

Fig. 7: Effect of fibre length on the composite non-linear behaviour in case of non linear matrix and without including damage

Fig 8: Prediction of stress-strain curve for tensile bar, including matrix non-linearity but without damage.

Damage

In order to approximate larger parts more closely, a moulded plaque was taken as representative of a part with expanding flow, to give better results than a simple tensile bar. The stress-strain properties of the plaque were measured by machining tensile bars from the plaque and performing uni-axial tensile testing. The average of the measured data is shown in Fig 9, with an indication of the spread in the data. The orientation and fibre length distributions of these plaques were measured and, together with the stress-strain data of the matrix material, were input into the model to predict the behaviour. Fig 9 shows the prediction without taking into account damage and with damage. As can be seen, the damage cause further non-linearity, similar to the measured data. The prediction lies within the spread of the measured data, on the low side.

Fig 9: Measurement and predictions for a moulded plaque

CONCLUSIONS

A micro-mechanical model based on Mori and Tanaka method has been developed to predict the tensile behaviour of long glass fibre reinforced polypropylene composites taking into account matrix non-linearity and damage. By making use of this model the effects of fibre length and orientation distributions on the overall behaviour of non-linear composites are also investigated. According to the results obtained, the macroscopic properties of LGFPP are highly dependent on its local microstructure.

The damage model predicts curves which are quite similar to the measured data and within the spread of the measurements. The predictions of the damage model can be improved by choosing a suitable treatment of damaged fibres which would be more realistic. In order to avoid such fast reduction of the stiffness properties once the composite is damaged, or to

better represent the damage evolution inside the material, experimental data based on microscopic observations would be useful.

The advantage of the model is that in addition of predicting the non-linear behaviour of LGFPP composites, it can also take into account the local variations of the microstructure generally influencing the overall mechanical properties of such composites. Finally, on one hand the model gives a better understanding of the behaviour of LGFPP and can be used for the optimisation of their reinforcement structure, but on the other hand it can also be a useful tool to predict the non-linear behaviour of discontinuous fibres or particles reinforced composite materials in general.

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